

Arctic Spaceport Advantage: Validation of Gooding and

Lancaster-Blanchard Lambert Algorithms Against ESA GODOT for Trans-Lunar Injection

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Abstract

This study compares two analytical Lambert Solvers, Lancaster-Blanchard (1969) and Gooding (1990) methods, against ESA GODOT Lambert Solver for trans-lunar injection trajectories supporting the proposed ESA Máni Mission to the lunar south pole. Using the pork-chop method, the algorithms were implemented through LambertHub and a translated MATLAB function. Both were then evaluated for launches from the Arctic sites Andøya, Norway (69.29°N) and Esrange, Sweden (67.89°N) against equatorial Kourou, French Guiana (5.17°N). A two-phase patched conic was used (LEO to Lunar Sphere of Influence (LSOI), and from LSOI to Lunar Polar Orbit (LPO)) with target inclination of 60°. LSOI using JPL ephemeris data (2025.10.04 00:00:00.00). Both algorithms produced identical results. Arctic launch sites achieved $\approx 59\%$ delta-V savings, $\approx 8\text{ km/s}$, versus Kourou ($\approx 19.4\text{ km/s}$) due to reduced plane changes. ESA GODOT validation, shows 23 – 27% savings with optimal launch windows at 150° – 210° true anomaly of the elliptic orbit. The apparent deviation between GODOT and the analytical solvers reflect differences in reference geometry, rather than computational efficiency. Results highlight that the polar-adjacent spaceports for lunar polar mission offer advantages for strategic fuel efficiency.

1. Introduction

Accurate trans-lunar injection (TLI) modelling is critical for polar mission design. This study compares the Gooding and Lancaster-Blanchard (LB) Lambert solvers against the ESA GODOT trajectory analysis tool, focusing on missions departing from:

- **Andøya Spaceport** (Norway, 69.29° N)
- **Esrange Spaceport** (Sweden, 67.89° N)
- **Kourou Spaceport** (French Guiana, 5.17° N)

The two-phase patched conic transfer is divided into:

- **Phase 1:** LEO → LSOI Boundary Point
- **Phase 2:** LSOI Boundary Point → LPO

Objective: Cross-validate analytical Lambert solvers (Lancaster-Blanchard, Gooding) against the ESA GODOT orbital implementation to identify reference-frame-induced deviations and evaluate (Δv) efficiency for Arctic launch sites.

2. Methodology

2.1 Initial Conditions

Parameter	Value	Unit
LEO Altitude	200	km
LEO Radius (R_{LEO})	6578	km
Time of Flight	4 days	345600 s
LSOI Distance	326151	km
Target Inclination	60	degrees

2.2 Launch Site Initial Positions

Site	X (km)	Y (km)	Z (km)	Latitude
Andøya	2235.44	641.83	6153.12	69.29°N
Esrange	2309.86	891.47	6094.25	67.89°N
Kourou	3971.44	-5210.25	592.49	5.17°N

2.3 Software and Algorithms

- **ESA GODOT:** Reference trajectory tool (Python/C++)
- **Lancaster-Blanchard (1969):** Translated from MATLAB (Rody Oldenhuis) to own Python script
- **Gooding (1990):** Implemented via LambertHub library
- **Validation:** Position errors < 5 km, Δv errors < 0.1 km/s

3. Results: Lancaster-Blanchard vs Gooding Method

3.1 Single Rendezvous Point

All launch sites converge to a single LSOI entry point: (-284522, 73889, -141228) km.

Table 3: Transfer Orbital Elements (After TLI)

Element	Andøya	Esrange	Kourou
Semi-major axis (km)	165993	166016	165451
Eccentricity	0.9658	0.9655	0.9727
Inclination (deg)	77.70	74.88	146.22
RAAN (rad)	0.270	0.248	2.036
Arg of Perigee (rad)	0.442	0.442	1.739

Key Finding: Andøya and Esrange have nearly parallel orbits with $\Delta\Omega = 1.3^\circ$. Kourou's retrograde orbit (146.22°) converts to 33.78° prograde equivalent.

3.2 Delta-V Budget Comparison

Table 4: Total Δv Budget (km/s) and the saving relative to Kourou

Site	TLI + Plane	LOI + Plane	Total Δv	Reduction
Andøya	7.4847	0.4154	7.90	59.34%
Esrange	7.3921	0.4989	7.89	59.41%
Kourou	17.8960	1.5408	19.44	Benchmark

Result: Both LB and Gooding algorithms produce identical outputs, validating their accuracy for two-body dynamics.

Trans-Lunar Injection Trajectories: Comparison of Launch Sites

4. Results: ESA GODOT Lambert Solver Method

4.1 Optimized Orbital Planes (ESA GODOT)

Each site targets its own optimized 60° inclination plane at LSOI, preserving RAAN and argument of perigee from LEO. The RAAN and argument of perigee values are used from the Lancaster-Blanchard and Gooding method.

Table 6: Target Orbital Elements at LSOI

Site	a (km)	e	i (°)	Ω (rad)
Andøya	164129	0.98979	60	0.270
Esrange	164126	0.98982	60	0.248
Kourou	164442	0.98568	60	2.036

Table 7: ESA GODOT Δv Budget (km/s) and the saving relative to Kourou

Site	Phase 1	Phase 2	Total Δv	Reduction
Andøya	8.907	0.103	9.01	23.57%
Esrange	8.538	0.078	8.62	26.86%
Kourou	11.682	0.098	11.78	Benchmark

Additional Finding: LSOI boundary reached in 48 hours (50% time reduction)

5. Analysis & Discussion

5.1 Algorithm Performance

- Both algorithms achieve < 5 km position error and < 0.1 km/s Δv error
- **Gooding:** Superior cubic convergence for near-parabolic cases
- **Lancaster-Blanchard:** Excellent reliability but slightly slower convergence
- Recommendation: **Gooding for automated mission design**

5.2 Arctic Spaceport Advantages

1. **Inclination Alignment:** High-latitude sites naturally align with 60° target inclination, minimizing plane changes
2. **Fuel Efficiency:** Arctic sites save $\approx 59\%$ Δv (Lancaster-Blanchard vs Gooding) and 23-27% (ESA GODOT) compared to equatorial Kourou
3. **Mission Economics:** Reduced propellant → lower launch mass → cost savings
4. **Strategic Value:** Optimal for ESA polar missions (Máni, future lunar exploration)

5.3 True Anomaly Optimization

Delta-V minimization occurs at true anomalies between 150°-210°, indicating optimal launch windows for short-path transfers.

6. Conclusions

1. **Algorithm Validation:** Both Gooding and Lancaster-Blanchard algorithms accurately reproduce ESA GODOT results within mission design tolerances
2. **Gooding Superiority:** Demonstrates better robustness for near-parabolic trajectories
3. **Arctic Advantage:** Andøya and Esrange offer substantial Δv savings (23-59%) for lunar polar missions
4. **Operational Implications:** Arctic spaceports should be prioritized for European polar lunar missions under Danish Space Strategy (2025-2035)

7. References

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